

Coupled CFD and Tritium Transport Modeling of a Permeator Probe for Tritium Concentration in Liquids

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Abstract

This work conducted multiphysics simulations of an α -Fe tritium permeator probe, a potential diagnostic for measuring tritium concentration in liquid breeders. The objective was to determine the relationships between LiPb inlet tritium concentration and flow rate on tritium permeation flux through the probe. Two probe positions were tested, with the probe in or out of the direct line of fluid flow. Computational fluid dynamics simulations were performed with OpenFOAM and results were fed into tritium transport code FESTIM. Generally, less than 1% of the total tritium flux permeated into the probe, demonstrating the probe is non-invasive. Behavior laws were derived to describe the impact of inlet concentrations (from 10^{-4} to 10^2 mol m⁻³) on permeation flux. Varying only the inlet concentrations, two permeation regimes were identified. At an inlet concentration of 10 mol m⁻³, in the *probe-in* case, the permeation flux was $\approx 3 \times 10^{18}$ T s⁻¹, and in the *probe-out* case, the permeation flux was $\approx 5 \times 10^{17}$ T s⁻¹. The impact of flow rate (from 1 kg s⁻¹ to 4 kg s⁻¹) on permeation flux varied with geometry: in the *probe-in* case having a negligible impact (< 3%) and in the *probe-out* case demonstrating a peak in permeation flux at 3 kg s⁻¹. These results were assessed against detectability limits of typical pressure gauges.

Keywords: Tritium, Permeation Against Vacuum, Permeator Probe, Nuclear fusion, Diagnostic.

1. Introduction

Tritium accountability is critical to the nuclear fusion fuel cycle and the self-sufficiency of fusion systems. Sensing technologies to measure tritium concentration throughout the fusion fuel cycle are essential to tracking tritium inventory and understanding the efficiency of various fuel cycle components. Existing tritium sensing technologies, however, apply to tritium in gas (eg. ion chambers [1]) or tritium in water using asynchronous liquid scintillation counting [2, 3]). Some of these are even concentration dependent, requiring a minimum concentration for sensor detection. There is no standardized technique for online measurement of tritium in liquids such as those used in fusion fuel cycles. Previous research has identified the potential use of hydrogen permeation sensors in liquid breeding blankets to provide real-time tritium concentration measurements [4, 5, 6]. Experiments existing thus far have tested permeation sensor, or “permeator probe” as referred to throughout this paper, performance when submerged in a breeding blanket material, while computational studies have provided simplified models to predict probe performance. This work is the first to develop a three-dimensional, high-fidelity model of a permeator probe with complete fluid-dynamic and tritium-transport physics.

Generally, permeator probes utilize the permeation-against-vacuum (PAV) principle. In the context of this paper, PAV is the process of tritium permeation from the liquid breeder, through the probe material, and into vacuum for recovery, as driven by a concentration gradient enforced by the vacuum. Various materials, including Nb [7], Inconel-625 [8], and α -Fe [9], have been tested as potential probe materials due to their high tritium permeability. α -Fe was chosen as the probe material in this work due to its high hydrogen diffusivity and compatibility with LiPb [6]; previous work has focused on α -Fe for these same reasons [10, 11, 12, 9].

Permeator probes can be operated in one of two modes: equilibrium or dynamic. Equilibrium mode requires that the probe is connected to a chamber initially at vacuum. As time passes, hydrogen concentration increases in the chamber until reaching a steady state equilibrium pressure. Most probes presented in literature have studied operation in equilibrium mode [4, 13, 12, 5, 6]. The time for the probe system to reach equilibrium pressure ranges from a few seconds to almost a full day [7].

Dynamic mode, on the other hand, directly measures the permeation flux across the permeator probe surface [6]. While some studies have assessed the impact of mass transfer coefficient on permeation flux [14, 8], much of this previous work is limited to one-dimensional, single material, and steady-state models that rely on analytical correlations. Due to its reliance on permeation flux, dynamic mode is also highly dependent on

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transport regime.

Tritium transport through permeator probes can occur in a diffusion-limited regime (DLR), a surface-limited regime (SLR), a liquid-limited regime (LLR), or some combination of any two (a mixed regime), as described by Alberghi *et al* [15]. In the DLR, it is assumed that tritium transport is limited by diffusion through the probe volume. Surface effects happen so fast in comparison to diffusion that they are negligible in overall transport. In the SLR, this assumption does not hold, and tritium transport becomes limited by the surface effects across the probe membrane (i.e., recombination and dissociation on the vacuum surface). Whether a system is in the DLR or SLR can be determined by calculation of permeation number, W , which expresses the ratio of diffusive transport through the probe to surface transport at the vacuum surface [16]. The LLR, on the other hand, assumes that tritium mass transport through the liquid breeder is slower than both diffusion through the probe and surface effects on the vacuum surface. Calculation of partition parameter, ζ , the ratio of diffusive transport through the probe to advective transport through the breeder, can be used to determine if a system lies within the LLR. In the case where no singular regime dominates, a mixed regime can occur. For instance, a system with slow mass transport that is also impacted by surface effects could be in a “liquid-dominated regime” (LDR). Permeation number and partition parameter determine the extent of each process’ domination for a system.

Crafting reliable and accurate permeator sensors depends on an array of factors, including sensor material, breeder flow, tritium concentration, operational mode (dynamic or equilibrium), and transport regime. This work presents a fully three-dimensional multiphysics simulation of a helical α -Fe permeator probe for use in LiPb. The probe was modeled under dynamic operating conditions, with all surface reactions explicitly included. OpenFOAM [17] was used to simulate the turbulent flow field of the LiPb breeder around the probe geometry. The velocity and turbulence fields produced from OpenFOAM were used in a tritium transport simulation using Finite Elements Simulation of Tritium in Materials (FESTIM) [18]. Two probe placements were considered. Their impact on pressure drops through the breeder and their intrusiveness was assessed. Using these tools, this work for each geometry presents relationships between permeation flux and inlet concentration and inlet velocity, as well as detectability performance.

2. Methodology

Two probe geometries were created in CAD and meshed in GMSH [19]. Each mesh was used to run CFD in OpenFOAM, producing velocity and turbulent viscosity fields, which were then passed to FESTIM tritium transport models. The workflow for this process is demonstrated in Figure 1.

2.1. Geometry

The geometries are named *probe-in* and *probe-out* to describe the scenarios with the probe in and out of the direct line of fluid flow, respectively. The helical permeator probe is

Figure 1: Multiphysics modeling workflow.

shown in Figure 2, with parameters described in Table 1. These parameters hold for both geometries, with variation only in the probe location.

Figure 2: 3D CAD model of helical probe with height, H , diameter, D , coil diameter, d , pitch between coils, α , and coil thickness, t , described in Table 1.

Table 1: Helical probe geometric parameters based on [10]. The probe has 8 coils.

Geometrical Parameter	Symbol	Value [cm]
Probe Height,	H	6
Probe Diameter	D	2.6
Coil Diameter	d	0.2
Coil Thickness	t	0.02
Pitch between coils	α	0.75

The *probe-in* and *probe-out* (see Figure 3) geometries share the same pipe parameters for the breeder in Table 2, with the exception of an additional compartment in the *probe-out* geometry. The probe-containing compartment of the *probe-out* geometry is shown in Figure 3c.

Table 2: Breeder geometric parameters.

Geometrical Parameter	Value [cm]
Breeder Length	20
Breeder Diameter	13.8
<i>probe-out</i> Compartment Diameter	6
<i>probe-out</i> Compartment Height	8

2.2. Fluid Dynamics

OpenFOAM was used to solve the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations in steady-state. Both probe models used *simpleFoam* to solve Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS)

Figure 3: 3D CAD model of probe geometries.

turbulence models. The *probe-in* geometry was solved with the $k - \epsilon$ and $k - \omega$ turbulence models, and the *probe-out* geometry was solved with the $k - \epsilon$ and SST $k - \omega$ turbulence models; comparisons between turbulence models for each geometry are described in Section 3.1. This work used each geometry's $k - \epsilon$ flow field as the initial guess for its respective $k - \omega$ model. The $k - \epsilon$ model is designed to best capture turbulence in steady, free-stream flow far from walls [20]. The $k - \omega$ and SST $k - \omega$ models differ slightly, in that the $k - \omega$ model is generally better suited for resolving turbulent flow around wall boundaries, while the SST $k - \omega$ model combines the $k - \epsilon$ and $k - \omega$ models to provide resolved turbulence near and far from wall boundaries [21]. Because most of the flow for the *probe-in* case is dominated by interactions with boundaries, the $k - \omega$ model was chosen. The flow in the *probe-out* case has a more comparable dependence on free-stream and boundary-sensitive flow, rendering SST $k - \omega$ the chosen model. These turbulence models required calculation of inlet velocity, Reynolds number, kinematic viscosity (ν), initial turbulence kinetic energy (k), initial turbulence dissipation rate (ϵ), and/or initial specific dissipation rate. Initial models used a flow rate of 1 kg s^{-1} to compare against similar published work [22]. In OpenFOAM, a parabolic velocity profile was established at the inlet using inlet velocity, v_{in} , as the maximum velocity value. For LiPb, an operational temperature, T , of 603.15 K is assumed [22]. The thermophysical properties of LiPb used in the OpenFOAM model for each geometry, including breeder density, ρ_b , and kinematic viscosity, ν , are described in Table 3.

CFD boundary conditions in this model were the same for both geometries, and included a no slip velocity boundary con-

Table 3: LiPb thermophysical properties used in OpenFOAM model, assuming a flow rate equal to 1 kg s^{-1} from [22].

Property	Value	Unit	Reference
ρ_b	9802	kg m^{-3}	[23]
ν	1.19×10^{-7}	$\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	[23]
v_{in}	7.69	mm s^{-1}	—
Re	8356	—	[21]
k	2.21×10^{-7}	$\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$	[24]
ϵ	1.32×10^{-10}	$\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$	[24]
ω	6.61×10^{-3}	s^{-1}	[25]

dition on all wall and probe surfaces, and standard wall functions for k , ν_t , ϵ , and ω . The kinematic pressure, p [$\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$], was set to zero at the outlet.

2.3. Tritium Transport

2.3.1. Bulk Physics

Tritium diffusive flux is given by Fick's First Law:

$$J = -D\nabla c_{\text{T}} \quad (1)$$

where D [$\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$] is the diffusion term and the mobile tritium concentration is c_{T} [T m^{-3}]. FESTIM [18] solves for the change in tritium concentration with

$$\frac{\partial c_{\text{T}}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (D\nabla c_{\text{T}}) + \mathbf{u}\nabla c_{\text{T}}. \quad (2)$$

In this work, an advection term, $\mathbf{u}\nabla c_{\text{T}}$, represented the effect of velocity on tritium transport, with \mathbf{u} representing velocity [m s^{-1}] (provided from OpenFOAM) [26]. The model assumed no trapping.

The tritium transport parameters of α -Fe and LiPb are outlined in Table 4. There is a large uncertainty of these parameters in literature. A rigorous uncertainty quantification study of these parameters is outside of the scope of this paper. Therefore, we chose to use mean values from the H-transport-materials (HTM) database v0.16 [27] for demonstration purposes.

2.3.2. Turbulence-assisted Diffusion

Turbulence is a diffusion-enhancing property, and this is represented in FESTIM via a turbulent diffusion term, D_{turb} :

$$D_{\text{turb}} = \frac{\nu_t}{\text{Sc}_t} \quad (3)$$

where turbulent viscosity, ν_t , is provided by OpenFOAM [30, 31]. Sc_t is the turbulent Schmidt number, a ratio of turbulent momentum diffusivity to mass diffusivity, in this case estimated as 0.7 [32, 33]. This is a standard method in advection-diffusion processes in turbulent systems [34, 35, 36].

Table 4: Material parameters used for LiPb FESTIM Model. Note that D_0 is the Fickian diffusivity. Diffusion coefficients, activation energies, and LiPb solubility values are taken as the mean of tritium values for that parameter available in HTM v0.16 [27].

Property	Material		Unit
	LiPb (Breeder)	α -Fe (Probe)	
Diffusion Coefficient, D_0	4.68×10^{-8}	9.38×10^{-9}	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
Diffusion Activation Energy, E_D	0.19	0.09	eV
Solubility Coefficient, K_{S_0}	1.62×10^{21}	3.07×10^{23} [28]	$\text{m}^{-3} \text{Pa}^{0.5}$
Solubility Activation Energy, E_{K_S}	0.17	0.28 [28]	eV
Recombination Coefficient, $K_{r,0}$	—	1.26×10^{-25} [29]	$\text{m}^4 \text{s}^{-1}$
Recombination Activation Energy, E_{K_r}	—	0.41 [29]	eV

2.3.3. Stabilisation Technique

At high mesh Péclet numbers, the Galerkin finite-element methods can experience nonphysical oscillations in the concentration solution. A stabilisation method can be used to maintain solution stability. In this model, an artificial diffusion term, in line with the *inconsistent stabilisation* method [37], is introduced to increase diffusivity in line with fluid flow, lowering the Péclet number throughout the mesh. The artificial diffusion term, D_{art} , is defined as

$$D_{\text{art}} = \delta h \|u\| \quad (4)$$

where $\|u\|$ is velocity magnitude and h is the cell size of the FESTIM mesh. δ is a tuning parameter whose true value is 0; lowest-as-possible values of δ that dampen nonphysical oscillations are optimal. δ were optimized for each geometry to produce realistic tritium concentration fields.

The total diffusion coefficient for LiPb then becomes equal to

$$D = D_{\text{Fick}} + D_{\text{turb}} + D_{\text{art}} \quad (5)$$

where D_{Fick} is the Fickian diffusion term, $D = D_0 \exp(-E_D/k_B T)$, with D_0 the diffusion coefficient [$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$], E_D [eV] the diffusion activation energy, k_B the Boltzmann constant of $8.617 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV K}^{-1}$, and T the temperature in K). D_0 and E_D for LiPb used in the model are described in Table 4.

2.3.4. Boundary Conditions

A surface recombination boundary condition was enforced on the vacuum surface of the probe:

$$J \cdot \mathbf{n} = -K_r c_T^2 \quad (6)$$

where J is the permeation flux and K_r is the surface recombination coefficient. K_r can be expressed by

$$K_r = K_{r,0} \exp\left[\frac{E_{K_r}}{k_B T}\right] \quad (7)$$

The pre-exponential recombination coefficient, $K_{r,0}$, for α -Fe and its corresponding surface recombination activation energy,

E_{K_r} , can be found in Table 4. In the diffusion-limited approximation, K_r approaches ∞ , and the recombination boundary condition of Equation 6 is replaced by a $c_T = 0$ boundary condition.

At the inlet, an arbitrary concentration value of $c_{\text{in}} = 10 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$ was used and later varied. On the walls, there is a no-flux boundary condition ($\mathbf{J} = 0$) for simplification purposes. Between the two materials (LiPb and α -Fe), conservation of chemical potential is enforced:

$$\frac{c_{T,\text{LiPb}}}{K_{S,\text{LiPb}}} = \frac{c_{T,\alpha\text{-Fe}}}{K_{S,\alpha\text{-Fe}}} \quad (8)$$

where $c_{T,\text{LiPb}}$ and $c_{T,\alpha\text{-Fe}}$ are the tritium concentrations in LiPb and α -Fe at the interface, respectively, and $K_{S,\text{LiPb}}$ and $K_{S,\alpha\text{-Fe}}$ are the corresponding solubility coefficients of each metal [18].

2.3.5. Evaluating a Pressure Rise from the Probe

Previous work has shown that dynamic mode measurements are made by measuring pressure changes within the capsule to which the permeator probe is attached [7]. To assess the suitability of this probe for common industrial instrumentation, a calculation was performed to estimate the pressure change corresponding to the minimum permeation flux in each geometry. The permeation flux into the probe, J , can be equated to a pressure rise, $\frac{dP}{dt}$, in a known volume using the ideal gas law as a rate:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = J \frac{RT}{N_A V} \quad (9)$$

where temperature T (603.15 K) and volume V are constant, R is the ideal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and N_A is Avogadro's number. In this experimental system, the change in pressure is calculated. The volume estimate for a system that consists of the permeator probe, some extra tubing (about 10 cm^3), and the internal volume representative of industry standard capacitance manometer (about 6.3 cm^3 [38]) is 48.16 cm^3 , or $4.816 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3$. Section 3.2.3 uses this method to comment on the tritium transport results.

3. Results

3.1. Fluid Dynamics

The *probe-in* velocity fields produced by the $k - \epsilon$ and $k - \omega$ models for a flow rate of 1 kg s^{-1} varied significantly (see Figure 4). In the $k - \epsilon$ model, velocity decreased to 50 % or less of u_{in} around the probe, with lowest values at the back end the probe. The effect of loose eddies can be seen in the probe region, creating local fluctuations in velocity magnitude. The free-stream flow was mostly unperturbed, except for immediately in the probe wake, in which velocity steadily decreased to about 65 % of u_{in} .

Figure 4: Velocity fields for *probe-in* geometry.

On the other hand, the $k - \omega$ model produced a maximum velocity one full order of magnitude higher than u_{in} , seen in Figure 4b. Local fluctuations presumably from tighter eddies occurred on the probe surface, increasing velocity compared to the $k - \epsilon$ case. The free-stream flow was generally unperturbed, but velocity values in the wake of the probe reached higher values than in the $k - \epsilon$ case.

The $k - \omega$ model was chosen as the flow field for import into FESTIM due to its aforementioned ability to better resolve near-boundary turbulence. This is reflected in its more detailed capture of oscillating velocities in the probe region in Figure 4b. The $k - \omega$ model converged in 208 iterations.

The ν_t field produced by OpenFOAM is important for turbulent diffusion. As visualized in Figure 5a, turbulent viscosity had highest magnitudes in regions surrounding the probe where the flow becomes more turbulent. The appearance of an buffer layer reflected the standard wall functions set in OpenFOAM; while ν_t increased diffusion around and in the center of the probe, ν_t affected permeation less due to its near-zero value

at the probe surface. Pressure variations can be seen in Figure 5b. The pressure drop from inlet to outlet was 0.28 Pa, a relatively low pressure drop when compared to ambient pressure and not a concern for operational pumping power.

Figure 5: Output turbulent viscosity and pressure fields for *probe-in* geometry. In addition to velocity field, the ν_t field is passed to FESTIM.

The *probe-out* velocity fields for a flow rate of 1 kg s^{-1} varied in their resolution of turbulence in the probe region (see Figure 6), but agreed on a laminar flow profile in the bulk. The $k - \epsilon$ model depicted one region of high velocity near the bottom of the probe, with a maximum velocity one full order of magnitude above v_{in} . North of this high-velocity region, the flow did not reach notable velocities, mostly 15 % or less of v_{in} . Little fluid mixing appeared to occur in the probe region in Figure 6a.

The SST $k - \omega$ model, shown in Figure 6b, resolved greater fluid circulation throughout the probe region, although the maximum velocity is only about 55 % of v_{in} . The flow in the probe region was anisotropic, and the maximum velocity occurred at the center of the helical probe. The circulating motion of the velocity profile demonstrated the impact of the compartment containing the probe, which introduced a higher dependence on wall-interactions than in the *probe-in* case, and encouraged turbulent flow as a result. Due to the importance of boundary interactions in this case, the SST $k - \omega$ flow field was chosen for input into FESTIM. The SST $k - \omega$ model converged in 2457 iterations.

The ν_t field of Figure 7a demonstrated high turbulent viscosity in the free-stream flow as well as regions of high velocity in the probe region. Diffusivity was expected to be higher in this case than that of *probe-in*, demonstrating that turbulent flow in this geometry encouraged slower fluid circulation that might increase permeation through the probe. The pressure field is depicted in Figure 7b. The pressure drop from inlet to outlet was

0.018 Pa, a full order of magnitude less than in the *probe-in* case. For this reason, the *probe-out* geometry is the more desirable CFD configuration for a permeator probe system given its almost negligible pressure change.

(a) $k - \epsilon$ velocity field.

(b) $k - \omega$ velocity field.

Figure 6: Velocity fields for *probe-out* geometry.

3.2. Tritium Transport

Permeation flux in both geometries was less than 1% of the tritium concentration in the breeder, demonstrating that the probe is non-invasive to the system. The tritium fields for the *probe-in* case with inlet concentration 10 mol m^{-3} and flow rate 1 kg s^{-1} are visualized in Figure 8. Permeation flux into the probe was found to be 0.609% of the inlet flux. Slower velocities around the probe allowed permeation to occur, creating concentrations in the breeder that were low where velocity was

(a) Turbulence viscosity, ν_t .

(b) Kinematic pressure relative to outlet, p .

Figure 7: Turbulence property fields for *probe-out* geometry.

low. The concentration appears uniform on the probe surface in Figure 8b, which can be explained by the uniform behaviour of the ν_t , and thus the diffusion coefficient on the probe surface. Permeation flux into the front half of the probe was too low to create a significant decrease in c_T on the back half of the probe. Tritium diffused symmetrically through the probe solid to vacuum, as expected.

Tritium concentrations fields for the *probe-out* case with the same c_{in} and breeder flow rate are depicted by Figure 9. Permeation flux in this case was 0.099% of the inlet flux. Concentration in the breeder was lowest where velocity was lowest (see Figure 6b), where most permeation occurs. Unlike in the *probe-in* case, the tritium concentration was not uniform on the outer surface of the probe. Tritium concentration was higher at the bottom of the probe, near the free-stream breeder flow, and also towards the $-y$ direction, where the breeder flow is coming from. This behavior may derive from the much lower ν_t values in the probe compartment than in the free-stream bulk; only a fraction of the tritium in the breeder makes it into the compartment at all. Tritium diffusion through the probe volume obeyed a similar profile as the *probe-in* case where the tritium surface concentration is highest (see Figure 9c). The *probe-out* geometry overall measured a permeation flux about an order

Figure 8: Tritium concentration fields for *probe-in* benchmark case with $c_{in} = 10 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$.

of magnitude less than that measured in the *probe-in* geometry.

These results indicate that the *probe-out* geometry is the ideal configuration for dynamic tritium concentration. While the absence of low concentration data for the *probe-out* case prevented the derivation of a SLR relationship, the low pressure drop from Section 3.1 indicates its benefit, but perhaps at the expense of a tritium concentration limit, due to its detection of permeation fluxes a full order of magnitude less than in the *probe-in* case.

The use of a stabilisation term (D_{art}) was one constraint on these results that could be improved. This model assumes only one isotope of hydrogen, tritium, when in reality, deuterium and protium will also be present in the fuel cycle. Multi-isotope models to test differences in transport could be used to optimise the permeator probe system. The model also assumed pure LiPb. Future studies should include impurities in LiPb to assess their effect on tritium transport.

3.2.1. Parametric Study of Inlet Concentration

A parametric study was conducted on each geometry to determine the impact of inlet concentration on permeation flux. For the *probe-in* geometry, inlet concentrations ranged from $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol m}^{-3}$ to $5 \times 10^1 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$. Figure 10a visualises the

Figure 9: Tritium concentration fields for *probe-out* case with $c_{in} = 10 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$ and flow rate 1 kg s^{-1} .

transition from the SLR to the DLR. In the surface-limited case, represented by the blue best-fit-line in Figure 10a, permeation flux was proportional to $c_{in}^{1.74}$, or about c_{in}^2 . Such proportionality indicates the relationship expressed by Equation 6, where surface phenomena are the permeation-limiting step for lower tritium concentration (SLR). The diffusion-limited case, represented by the orange best-fit-line of Figure 10a, shows permeation flux as proportional to $c_{in}^{1.12}$, or about c_{in} . For higher tritium concentrations, the flux-concentration relationship obeyed Fick's Law (see Equation 2), and surface effects became negligible when compared to diffusive transport through the probe.

While it appears the DLR and SLR have been identified, the non-exact proportionality of flux to c_{in}^2 or c_{in} suggests a mass-transport effect. In fact, calculating partition parameter [15] (which does not change from SLR to DLR) reveals that the *probe-in* system was in the LDR. Tritium transport was not completely dominated by surface effects in the SLR-like case, or diffusive transport in the DLR-like case, but was partially

(a) *probe-in*.

(b) *probe-out*.

Figure 10: Parametric study for demonstrating impact of inlet concentration on permeation flux at flow rate 1 kg s^{-1} .

dominated by mass transport. Thus, the non-exact relationships between flux and inlet concentration. For the concentrations shown in Figure 10b, permeation flux was proportional to $c_{\text{in}}^{1.21}$, indicating a less strong diffusion dominance on tritium transport. This is reflected in a slightly higher partition parameter (as opposed to the *probe-in* case), but ultimately, this system is also in the LDR.

3.2.2. Parametric Study of Flow Rate

A second parametric study was conducted on each geometry to determine the influence of breeder flow rate on permeation flux. Flow rates from 1 kg s^{-1} to 4 kg s^{-1} were tested. Figure 11 demonstrates the nonlinear relationship between permeation flux and flow rate for the *probe-in* geometry. Flux appears to plateau at fast flow rates, but even in the jump from 1 kg s^{-1} to 2 kg s^{-1} , varies by less than 3%. Flow rates within this range thus have a negligible impact on permeation flux. Future work

should test flow rates outside of this range to determine if flux is maximized at a certain rate.

Figure 11: Parametric study demonstrating impact of breeder flow rate on permeation flux for $c_{\text{in}} = 10 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$.

The *probe-out* geometry, on the contrary, demonstrates a peak in permeation flux at 3 kg s^{-1} in Figure 11. Given that the probe in the *probe-out* geometry was situated out of the direct line of fluid flow, fast flow rates may have prevented tritium from escaping into the probe region at all, decreasing permeation flux dramatically at 4 kg s^{-1} . Existence of a peak in flux at 3 kg s^{-1} suggests that a flow rate for maximum permeation flux exists, is not necessarily the slowest flow rate, and could be further optimized. Future work should address the relationship between permeation flux and low inlet concentration for the *probe-out* case.

3.2.3. Evaluation of Experimental Relevance

Equation 9 was used to determine if the permeation fluxes produced in this work are relevant for experimental measurement capabilities. The lowest permeation flux between both geometries was estimated as $1 \times 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which produces a change in pressure of $1.78 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa s}^{-1}$, or $1.41 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$. Given an arbitrary change in time, Δt , pressure changes of this magnitude produce absolute pressure values that reach detectability limits for high vacuum pressure gauges [39] within 10 minutes. Permeation fluxes in this study above about $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (creating pressure changes around $0.013 \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$) reach detectability limits of more conventional digital manometers in less than 1 minute. The entire range of permeation fluxes in this study are thus measurable.

Permeation flux can also be measured directly from a mass spectrometer with continuous vacuum pumping; previous experiments have measured as low as $4.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Pa s}^{-1}$ with this method [7]. This work could be extended in the future to include assessment against mass spectroscopy detectability limits. Comparison to actual experimental data [10] would improve the results of this study. Response time of the probe was not tested but becomes relevant when relating flux to a pressure

change. Transient simulations in FESTIM can be used to test response time in future iterations.

3.2.4. Validity of the Diffusion-Limited Approximation

Models with the diffusion-limited approximation were also produced for comparison. As seen in Figure 12a, the diffusion-limited approximation overestimated permeation flux when in the SLR by one to two orders of magnitude. At low tritium concentrations, surface phenomena cannot be neglected. As the system approaches the DLR, the diffusion-limited approximation became more accurate, verifying the previous identification of the diffusion-limited dependence, but still overshooting flux values. In the *probe-out* case, the diffusion-limited approxima-

(a) *probe-in* .

(b) *probe-out* .

Figure 12: Comparison of Diffusion-Limited Approximation and Full Model with all surface reactions on permeation flux.

tion was almost identical to the DLR flux values (see Figure 12b), again verifying the regime as diffusive transport dependent. This is unexpected, given that flux in the *probe-out* case was less proportional to c_{in} than in the *probe-in* case (i.e., for *probe-in*, $c_{in}^{1.12}$ and for *probe-out*, $c_{in}^{1.21}$).

4. Conclusion

A 3D helical permeator probe in two configurations was simulated with OpenFOAM for CFD and FESTIM for tritium transport. The *probe-in* and *probe-out* models varied in their placement of the probe with respect to the fluid flow. In both cases, probe permeation fluxes were less than 1% of the total tritium flux, demonstrating the probe to be non-invasive. The *probe-in* geometry consistently measured permeation fluxes an order of magnitude greater than those in the *probe-out* geometry, but the *probe-out* geometry produced a pressure drop one order of magnitude less than the *probe-in* case.

The *probe-in* inlet concentration parametric study suggested that as the inlet concentration increases, surface effects become less dominant. As a result, the permeation flux power-law dependence changes. For the *probe-in* case, the flow rate has a negligible impact on permeation flux. In the *probe-out* case, permeation flux was found to peak at 3 kg s^{-1} and then decrease at faster flow rates.

The permeation flux estimations in both configurations were tested against detectability limits in relevant pressure gauges. In both cases, pressure rises due to the permeation flux were within detectability limits.

Given the low pressure drop, the *probe-out* geometry seems to be a better configuration for a future permeator probe system, but possibly at the expense of a higher tritium detectability limit. Future work should validate both geometries against available experimental data on permeation flux. This study was limited to steady state simulations. In order to investigate response time, another key performance metric, the model would have to be extended to transient.

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